

Speculation on Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and Photon Spin

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The spin matrices (related to the 2x2 Pauli matrices) emerge from the linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation as shown by Dirac. This equation follows from the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m^2$ ($c=1$) which applies to a particle with rest mass and a photon if $m_0=0$. Furthermore, the Klein-Gordon solution $\exp(-iEt+i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$ applies to both a particle with rest mass and a photon. We have suggested in a previous note (1) that this function is directly related to the square root of an expression demonstrating translational invariance in time and space. The operators which yield E and \mathbf{p} vector, namely $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{grad}$ are proportional to the generators of translation

The spin matrix of a photon (spin 1), i.e. the Levi-Civita symbol ϵ_{ijk} with i denoting the matrix and jk elements, follows from a completely different equation, namely a continuity equation involving electromagnetic energy and the Poynting vector.

In this note, we investigate why photon spin emerges from the linearization of the continuity equation, while spin $\frac{1}{2}$ emerges from the linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation, when $-E^2 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m^2$ applies to both a particle with rest mass and a photon ($m_0=0$).

$\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and Translational Invariance

We argue that $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, namely the quantum free particle wavefunction, which is a solution of both the Klein-Gordon and nonrelativistic Schrodinger equations, emerges from translational invariance. In other words, for a free particle one does not require either of these equations to obtain the $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ form.

A free particle travels in time and space at a constant rate. There is a sense of translational invariance in both of these variables which may be described by a constant, i.e.

1 demonstrates translational invariance in time and space ((1))

Mathematically, the generators of a translation in time and space are:

$i\partial/\partial t$ and grad ((2))

If one takes the square root (in the sense of $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$) of ((1)) and seeks a periodic solution (i.e. one that does not diminish in t or r) then a solution is:

$\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ ((3))

In such a case, vital information, namely E energy and \mathbf{p} momentum are encapsulated in the square root and $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-i \text{grad}$ are not only generators of translations, but yield these important pieces of information. A minus sign factor for E allows for periodic 0 values of the phase if: $t \rightarrow t + n \text{ constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + n \text{ constant}/p$ where n is an integer.

One may note that $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ is a Lorentz invariant. Thus ideas of special relativity emerge directly from this translational invariance approach, with no mention of rest mass. In other words the phase of the function $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ remains constant as seen in frames moving with constant velocity $-v$.

This suggests a direct link with another Lorentz invariant, namely:

$$-E^2 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{with } E \rightarrow i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial and } \mathbf{p} \rightarrow -\text{grad partial}$$

This then yields the Klein-Gordon equation which has $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ as a solution. In the nonrelativistic limit, the Klein-Gordon equation becomes the Schrodinger equation.

Particles with Rest Mass and the Photon

The above discussion of invariance leading to $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ holds for any object moving with a constant velocity. In other words, it should apply to both a particle with rest mass (nucleon, electron) and a photon. Both have E and \mathbf{p} . The Lorentz invariant ((4)) contains m_0 which is rest mass and so applies to a particle which contains rest mass. If, however, one sets $m_0=0$, then ((4)) may apply to a photon. $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is a solution regardless.

An issue, however, which arises is the question of spin. Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation to find spin matrices (linked with Pauli matrices). In a previous note (1), we argued that since translation invariance leads to the form $\exp(-iEt + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ associated with the translational generators d/dt and grad , rotational invariance in the Klein-Gordon equation, namely $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, should lead, when this equation is linearized, to rotational generators and an associated state.

We suggested that \mathbf{p} vector be replaced with:

$$A = p(x) S_x + p(y) S_y + p(z) S_z \quad ((5)) \quad \text{such that } A^* A = \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$$

In other words, one multiplies two generalized numbers instead of using a vector operation. If:

$$S_x S_x = S_y S_y = S_z S_z = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad S_x S_y + S_y S_x = S_x S_z + S_z S_x = S_y S_z + S_z S_y = 0 \quad ((6))$$

one obtains $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$. The 2x2 Pauli matrices accomplish this goal. Eigenvectors for S_z are $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$ which imply rotation in one direction or the other.

The question we ask is: Why does this result only hold for a particle with rest mass and not a photon when a photon is also a solution of $-E^2 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2$, with $m_0=0$.

The Situation of Rest Mass

In the above section, we considered linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation, in particular $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, to obtain the Pauli matrices. $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. Why don't the Pauli matrices then apply to a photon? We saw that $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$ are eigenvectors which may be interpreted in terms of rotation in one direction or the other. It

seems, however, that one requires a frame in which to observe rotation. We call such a frame a rest frame. This, however, only applies to a particle with rest mass, not a photon.

A furthermore point is that ((4)) contains m_0 which then yields the photon solution when one sets $m_0=0$. This means that ((4)) is originally derived for a particle with rest m_0 . (If one were to start with an equation for a photon, no m_0 would ever appear). In fact, a derivation of $-E^2 + p^2 = -m_0^2$ and $-Et + px = \text{constant}$ follows from:

$$\text{Rest frame } m_0 \quad x=0, t \quad ((7))$$

((7)) does not apply to a photon, only to a particle with rest mass. If one considers a frame moving at a constant velocity $-v$, then m_0 is moving with v and x', t' should satisfy:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((8))$$

One may consider a unitary 2x2 transformation which achieves this, i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} f(v) & vf(v) \\ -vf & f \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |x| \\ |t| \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |x'| \\ |t'| \end{pmatrix} \quad ((8))$$

Using ((7)) and unitarity shows that: $f(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/b^2}$ where b is an unknown constant with units of 1/velocity. If ((8)) applies to (x,t) and (p,E) as well, one has ((4)), but for a particle with rest mass, not a photon. One may, however, set $m_0=0$ and the equation holds for a photon, but the derivation above does not. The derivation explicitly makes use of a rest frame. The translational invariance argument, however, given in the first section applies a priori to both a photon and a particle with rest mass and also leads to special relativity.

Thus, linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation to deal with $p \cdot p$ yields spin matrices for a particle with rest mass because the solution seems to imply rotation in a rest frame. What does one do in the case of a photon?

Photon Spin

We argue that given that a photon is a solution (or rather $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$ is) of ((4)) with $m_0=0$, and the appearance of $p \cdot p$, there should be some kind of rotational invariance associated with a photon as well. One cannot, however, linearize ((4)) to obtain the Pauli matrices for a photon because they imply rotation in a rest frame which does not exist for a photon. How does one resolve this issue?

The presence of m_0 implies a rest frame. The linearization of $p \cdot p$ (due to rotational invariance) leads to S_x, S_y, S_z which leads to the sense of rotation in the rest frame. m_0 is also responsible for energy and linked directly to momentum. Thus the creator of momentum, m_0 , so to speak, is also directly linked to spin.

A photon has energy and momentum, but how does it arise? It does not follow from a rest mass which is suddenly in motion as seen in a moving frame. We suggest it must follow from another equation which is consistent with translational invariance $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$, which in turn is consistent with special relativity. Thus something else creates photon momentum, but this

should be linked with rotational invariance, we argue. It would be good if this rotational invariance, however, does not depend on any kind of rest frame. In such a case, one might speculate there is a kind of rotational invariance between two kinds of objects which together create momentum and energy for a photon. This bypasses any kind of rest frame, as rotation pertains to one object relative to the other. These should follow an equation which is consistent with $E = |\mathbf{p}| c$ for a photon.

Furthermore, since $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ create clock and ruler divisions, i.e. \hbar/E and \hbar/p , it would be nice if the objects associated with rotational invariance created the 3-axis i.e. x,y,z . The momentum vector only creates one dimension. All of these ideas together are consistent with the continuity equation which follows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (a\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + b \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((9)) \quad a,b,d \text{ are constants}$$

\mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are 3-vectors representing the electric and magnetic fields of a photon. Thus, because a photon has no rest mass, one needs a separate equation associated with the entities which are responsible for momentum and also linked with rotational invariance. The Klein-Gordon equation contains m_0 which is responsible for the existence of momentum for a particle with rest mass, so one may directly linearize this equation to find rotational operators, i.e. the Pauli spin matrices. \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} together with \mathbf{p} vector define the coordinate axis and \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} create momentum and energy for a photon. They are thus linked to $\exp(-iEt+i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which is a solution of the Klein-Gordon equation. \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are perpendicular which is a rotationally invariant condition. This condition leads to the rotational invariance one seeks, i.e. one that is not linked to a rest frame. If one linearizes ((9)), one obtains an equation containing $\text{eijk grad} (\mathbf{E} + i \mathbf{B}) \cdot \mathbf{k}$, where grad represents the translational generator (linked with momentum) and eijk (the Levi Civita symbol from $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ (i) = $\text{eijk} E_j B_k$) represents a spin matrix for spin 1. "I" denotes the matrix and jk its elements.

For the photon, one requires a second quadratic equation to find spin and cannot simply linearize the Klein-Gordon equation which is custom made for a particle with rest mass m_0 which is the source of momentum and implies a rest frame. Due to translational invariance, however, the Klein-Gordon equation with $m_0=0$ yields a correct result for the photon, but not for its spin, when linearized.

A key idea seems to be that the quantity (quantities) associated with the creation of momentum (m_0 for a particle, \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{B} for a photon) also play a key role in spin. m_0 defines a rest frame in which physical rotation may exist while \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are rotated relative to each other which ultimately leads to eijk as the spin matrix.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the Lorentz invariant $-\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2 c^2$ holds for a particle with rest mass and a photon if $m_0=0$. Another Lorentz invariant is $-\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{t}$. We suggest that this follows directly from translational invariance i.e. from a constant number say 1. If one takes the square root (i.e. $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)=1$) and insists on a periodic solution, a solution is $\exp(-iEt+i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. The generators of translation d/dt and grad yield the key information pieces \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{p} vector. This argument holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. $-\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{t}$ is also

consistent with special relativity. The minus in front of E allows for periodic zero values i.e. $t \rightarrow t + n \text{ constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + n \text{ constant}/p$.

Another Lorentz invariant $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$, however, is custom made for a particle with rest mass. Rest mass m_0 implies a rest frame and is the source of momentum for such a particle. If one tries to linearize the rotationally invariant $p \cdot p$, one obtains Pauli matrices and eigenvectors $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ which imply rotation in a rest frame. A photon does not have such a frame because its momentum does not follow from a rest mass.

We argue that one must find the source of the photon's energy and momentum in the form of a quadratic equation which contains rotational invariance. Linearizing this equation should yield the spin matrix for a photon. This equation, however, must preserve translational invariance which is also found in $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$. Thus $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ should still be a solution for the photon. We argue that the continuity equation involving E and B (electric and magnetic field vectors) for a photon satisfies this condition and it is this equation which must be linearized for the photon. No rest frame is needed to deal with rotational invariance as there is a 90 degree rotation between E and B .

Thus it seems that the source of momentum, m_0 for a particle and E, B for a photon, are directly linked to spin.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Spin as an Operator on a Physical State which Replaces Vector Operations? Part 3 (preprint, zenodo, 2023)